

LANGUAGE IMPAIRMENTS AND USEFUL TEACHING STRATEGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. In terms of the organization of the lesson, the classic present, practice and perform model, where careful input of a particular structure is typically followed by controlling, less controlled and freer practice is likely to have been replaced by a more task-based approach, possibly on the lines of test, teach, test, where the learners are given a communicative task which is monitored by the teacher and then their language use while performing the task is fine-tuned by the teacher in a lesson stage which focuses on error correction or a particular form that is causing difficulties.

Key words: task-based approach, degree of linguistic accuracy, audio-visual activity, desired results, various combinations, multimedia, input, achieve desired results.

Introduction. Nowadays, probably most present-day practitioners would like to think that their classes are "communicative" in the widest sense of the word. Their lessons probably contain activities where learners communicate and where tasks are completed by means of interaction with other learners. To this end there will probably be considerable if not extensive use of pair, group and mingling activities, with the emphasis on completing the task successfully through communication with others rather than on the accurate use of form. During these activities the teacher's role will be to facilitate and then to monitor, usually without interruption, and then to provide feedback on the success or otherwise of the communication and, possibly, on the linguistic performance of the learners in the form of post-activity error

correction. In terms of the organization of the lesson, the classic present, practice and perform model, where careful input of a particular structure is typically followed by controlling, less controlled and freer practice is likely to have been replaced by a more task-based approach, possibly on the lines of test, teach, test, where the learners are given a communicative task which is monitored by the teacher and then their language use while performing the task is fine-tuned by the teacher in a lesson stage which focuses on error correction or a particular form that is causing difficulties. This is typically followed by a further task-based stage, where the initial task is repeated or a similar task is performed, ideally with a greater degree of linguistic accuracy than during the first attempt.

Main part. It's important to involve students in the learning process actively. This is generally done at the elementary level, but, in some cases, gets lost, especially at the lessons. That's why, involving students makes the subject more interesting to them. It also helps them retain the material and fosters critical thinking.

There are some teaching methods that turn students off during the lessons. They are: daily lectures, reading aloud from the textbook and watching audio-visual with little preparation or follow-up. Following are three ways to work with course materials and keep students involved and learning. Alternative to daily lectures power point presentations have made this relatively easy. The problem is that if it is done too often students tune out or turn off. At the beginning of the semester students will take notes and pay attention to what they are writing. After a steady diet of this, they will copy what is on the screen, paying little attention to what they write. When it is noticed by the teacher, you can be sure the "tune out" button has been pushed.

The solution is don't lecture every day. Find other ways to deal with the material. When you do lecture, involve students. Stop and ask questions: How, Why, What, etc. Ask them to summarize the important points. One of the keys to successful teaching is asking students what they learned from a particular lesson. Keep them involved, and they are more likely to remember the material.

Next alternative way is reading aloud during the lessons. As a teacher, one method that some teachers use which may be considered tuning out process is watching students read aloud from a textbook. Most often this is done because there aren't enough textbooks for each student to have one to take home. The other excuse may be that many students don't or won't do homework, so this gets the material covered. If you observe the students in a class where this is being done, you will notice that the majority are not following along.

There is an alternative to textbook reading aloud. Assign students to groups. Instruct them to read the section you have assigned and write down the main ideas. You can circulate to be sure groups are on task and answer questions. A group leader can then write the major points on the board. You can discuss them, fill in missing content and tie the sections together. I have seen this work many times. Students pay attention to their peers. You have made this a class activity by involving the students.

Another very important process is audio-visual activity, which can help the teacher to organize very interesting classes. But in some cases, it could be an activity where students will "tune out". There is a tremendous number of audio-visual materials for any subject, but how you use them is important. If you don't create a way for involving students this becomes a passive activity. That's why in order to achieve desired results:

- Be sure to introduce what you are going to show. Tie it to what they are learning. If it is long, break it up into two segments.

- Have them take notes or fill out a worksheet. Follow up with a discussion. This is vital if your students are going to get something out of the presentation. What did they learn? What was important? How does it tie in to the unit? These are just some of the follow-up questions which can be used during the lessons.

Conclusion. Involving students is important to create an environment where students look forward to coming to class. It is important to the overall learning

process. A few changes to lecturing, textbook reading and audio-visual presentations can help any teacher reach this goal. Multimedia is various combinations of text, graphics, sound, video and animation. It can be controlled, coordinated and delivered on a computer screen and implies interactivity which means the user is engaged in the presentation of information. In addition, multi-media can act as a more 'capable peer' as well as be a tool for student-student and student-teacher interaction. It can lead to more collaborative learning experiences while allowing students to learn with multi-media or from multi-media. The brain recognizes the given information much more in the visual way. Comprehension can often only occur after students are able to construct a mental image of what is meant. Once the student forms a mental image, then the concept is 'understood'. Therefore, the more visual we make learning, the greater the amount of subject matter that can be memorized and retained. Keeping your classroom active and student centered helps support the entire learning process.

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